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Indigenous Entrepreneurship. Current issues and future lines

Abstract

This paper contributes to a comprehensive understanding of the research field of Indigenous Entrepreneurship (IE), by analysing previous literature and proposing relevant future research lines. IE has been considered in the literature as key for the development of indigenous communities and a promising emergent area of research, and it is time to make efforts to integrate existing knowledge and approaches in order to advance the field. By analysing 264 papers related to IE published up to December 2020, we found some relevant results. As conclusions, we mention the heterogeneity and fragmentation of the field, the specificity of sociocultural issues and context, the concentration of studies in some geographical areas, the relevance of the individual level of study, and the combination of economic and social objectives. In addition, future integration efforts that contribute to a better generalisability of the empirical results and to theory building are proposed.

Keywords: Indigenous Entrepreneurship, Literature review, Empirical studies, Current issues.

Introduction

Between five and six percent of the entire world population is indigenous, around 476 million of people, spread in 90 countries (FAO 2021; World Bank 2021). In the last 20 years, indigenous people's rights have been improved through different instruments and mechanisms,

such as sustaining the economic growth and livelihoods of these communities and implementing cultural conservation and development, nowadays also contributing to the Sustainable Development Goals (World Bank 2021). In this sense, Indigenous Entrepreneurship (IE) has been shown to promote self-determination, economic independence, and traditions in indigenous communities (Henry, Dana, and Murphy 2018), and to be a promising emergent area of research (Hindle and Moroz 2010).

In this regard, several different aspects of IE have been studied in the last years, such as culture (e.g., Espeso-Molinero, Carlisle, and Pastor-Alfonso 2016), informal economy (e.g., Scarborough 2010), subsidies (e.g., Papanek 2006), women IE (e.g., Witbooi and Ukpere 2011) and many others. However, there have been only a few efforts to integrate this diversity of approaches. Specifically, to the knowledge of the authors, there are only two systematic literature reviews on the topic of IE (published in a Journal Citation Report – JCR – indexed journal): Hindle and Moroz (2010) in the *International Entrepreneurship and Management Journal* and Croce (2017) in the *Journal of Management & Organization*. The first study carried out an exhaustive review of the literature on IE in order to offer their own research framework in which to advance. The second study performed a review of the literature on IE to address the fit in different contexts of traditional models of entrepreneurship (urban, remote and rural). Besides, other studies conducted reviews, as the basis for developing conceptual papers, such as the pioneering work of Dana (1997) about the origins of self-employment in ethnocultural communities, Wood and Davidson's (2011) study about indigenous small business entrepreneurship in Australia or Croce's (2020) research about Indigenous women entrepreneurs. Subsequently, Jongwe et al. (2020) conducted a specific literature review about strategic business alliances in general and corporate/Indigenous community partnerships in particular.

As is known, systematic literature reviews play an essential role in academic research to gather existing and disperse knowledge and to examine the state of a specific field. It helps to build its theoretical framework and identify future research lines unexplored (Combs et al. 2020; Dabić et al. 2020; Linnenluecke, Marrone, and Singh 2020; Sharma et al. 2021; Snihur et al. 2021). In this sense, in order to contribute to a better and up-to-date understanding of IE as a sub-field of research on entrepreneurship, in this work, a systematic literature review is conducted. As a result, a general vision of the field as well as several research topics were found and analysed. A summary of this analysis, as IE research framework, together with the proposal of future research lines, constitute the main contributions of the paper.

Conceptual framework

Indigenous people are people whose ancestors were living in an area prior to colonisation or prior to the formation of a nation state (Dana 2007). However, there is not a consensus on a common definition of the term ‘indigenous’. In this vein, the ILO Convention No. 169 establishes that an indigenous person is a *“descent from populations, who inhabited the country or geographical region at the time of conquest, colonisation or establishment of present state boundaries. They retain some or all of their own social, economic, cultural and political institutions, irrespective of their legal status”* (ILO 1989, article 1). Subsequently, in recent years, indigenous has been recognised in the literature with self-identification as a way of determination of being indigenous. This means that today, far more important than how any scholar or government agency defines indigeneity, is the way indigenous people define themselves (Hindle and Moroz 2010).

On the other hand, IE includes any type of entrepreneurial activity or self-employment based on indigenous knowledge by indigenous people. IE is the ability of indigenous communities to use the resources available in their environment to achieve self-sufficiency and self-determination (April and Itenge 2020). Also, IE is a distinct disciplinary field of science (Hindle and Moroz 2010) which considers the creation, management and development of new ventures by indigenous people for the benefit of indigenous people (Hindle and Lansdowne 2005).

IE differs from other forms of entrepreneurship in terms of the context of the enterprise, the types of goals and outcomes on which the enterprise is focused, and/or the form and organisation of the enterprise (Cahn 2008), and, as mentioned, is sufficiently distinguished from other fields of research (Hindle and Moroz 2010). It differs mainly in the entrepreneurial spirit, as, from an indigenous perspective, entrepreneurship does not pursue economic benefit as a priority (April and Itenge 2020). Therefore, IE is a foundation for understanding indigenous enterprise, in which indigenous entrepreneurs are those who create and operate such entities (Henry, Newth, and Spiller 2017).

Consequently, in this paper, IE has been defined as any type of entrepreneurial activity or self-employment in any type of sector, based on indigenous knowledge/culture, by people who are themselves identified as indigenous people, and where the outcomes may extend to enterprise partners and stakeholders beyond the indigenous community.

Methodology

Applying the summarised concepts, and in order to take stock of previous academic knowledge about IE, we conducted a multi-stage method (Tranfield, Denyer, and Smart 2003) (see Figure 1). Specifically, following Hindle and Moroz (2010) and Jongwe et al. (2020), we started

from a classification of the search results without restrictions to move on to a reading of the selected works. This allowed us to identify the main topics, in addition to classifying the works based on a series of characteristics that are exposed in the data analysis. We conducted the search of papers during the first quarter of 2021, including papers published up to 31 December 2020.

INSERT FIGURE 1 HERE

Stage 1: database search

To identify the relevant literature published in well-recognised journals, and akin to previous studies, we selected two well-known and frequently used academic databases. Firstly, the *Web of Science of Clarivate Analytics* (formerly *ISI Web of Knowledge*), that includes publications listed in the *Journal Citation Reports* (JCR) and in the *Emerging Source Citation Index* (ESCI), which collects the journals that are being tracked to go to the JCR. Secondly, the SCOPUS database of Elsevier, which includes papers included in the *Scimago Journal & Country Rank* (SJR). Both databases are considered worldwide as two of the main repositories of scientific articles published in peer-reviewed journals, and have been used in recent literature reviews, such as the ones of Durán, Del Río, and Álvarez (2017) and Reis, Fleury, and Cavalho (2020).

We detail the followed search criteria next (see Table 1). First, for the JCR – Social Science Citation Index, 7,793 papers were found. After being filtered by entrepreneur* in title, abstract or keywords, there remained 280 papers. Second, for the ESCI, 3,252 papers were found in the first search, and there were 211 after we filtered them. Third, for the SJR, 602 papers were found. Scopus allowed us to directly filter by the keywords used in the papers. There were left 241 papers.

INSERT TABLE 1 HERE

In total, we obtained a volume of 732 papers, but many of them were indexed in several of the databases analysed simultaneously, so we proceeded to eliminate duplications and a total of 494 papers were obtained.

Stage 2: inclusion/exclusion criteria

We stipulated the inclusion/exclusion criteria in order to determine whether the papers should be retained for further analysis. The inclusion criteria contained two delimitations. Firstly, the IE area had to be a clear, identifiable concept studied in the paper. For the second delimitation, successively, the authors commented the publications selected. In case of doubt or disagreement, the introduction and conclusion sections of the paper in question were read.

After reading these articles, 253 papers were proposed for deletion (false positives); since it was considered that they did not address the subject of this review. Two researchers examined each of them before confirming their elimination. We obtained a database of 241 articles.

Stage 3: revision of previous literature review papers and other relevant references

In the search carried out, as mentioned before, we found two main literature review articles on IE. These reviews were from Hindle and Moroz (2010) and Croce (2017). Hindle and Moroz (2010) dealt with 102 papers published in JCR journals, but also with other indexes, books and conferences. Subsequently, Croce (2017) analysed 44 relevant written-in-English articles identified in selected electronic databases and manual searches of Australian Business Deans Council ranked journals from January 1, 1995 to the end of 2016. We decided, following Linnenluecke, Marrone, and Singh (2020), to crosscheck the references of these reviews with our results to detect possible gaps in our found list. The crosscheck showed that all the documents analysed by Hindle and Moroz (2010) and Croce (2017) that were indexed in JCR, ESCI or SJR were part of our selection.

On the other hand, using the references in the collected articles through the snowballing method, followed in similar studies such as van Burg, Elfring, and Cornelissen (2021), we added additional papers. Furthermore, the contributions of the reviewers, as specialists in the field, lead us to revise again the previous stages, deleted two papers, and include additional papers. In short, we completed the selection with 25 more works. That is, a total of 264 papers have been analysed in this review.

Stage 4: data extraction

We summarised in a spreadsheet file the 264 publications that resulted from the database search stage (title, author, journal, year published, keywords and abstract). Subsequently, four researchers analysed the information collected from the 264 publications separately. In doing so, we minimised the research subjectivity in the data extraction stage (Tranfield, Denyer, and Smart 2003).

Stage 5: data analysis

We adopted a *qualitative approach*, using content analysis and text coding techniques. Specifically, taking the sample of papers selected previously, we used an inductive method to define categories in order to address different aspects of the phenomenon studied (Corbin and Strauss 1990). In addition, we followed Davidsson and Wiklund's (2001) advice on resolving ambiguous classifications and categorisations through careful deliberation between the authors, minimising the research subjectivity in the data analysis. The review allowed us to develop a database in a spreadsheet file with different elements, for example, orientation (empirical, conceptual, literature review), method (qualitative, quantitative, theoretical) and main topics studied (non-indigenous culture, environmentally sustainable activities, institutions, indigenous culture and values, entrepreneurial motivation, social capital, education, family and personality

traits, among others). The analysis of the information collected in this database enabled us to obtain the results that we present next.

Results

General results

The results will be summarised next according to these specific characteristics: year of publication, indexation, orientation, methods and indexation, specific methods of the empirical works, main journals, main authors, unit of analysis, geographical areas, and subjects and keywords.

Year of publication

Firstly, the years of publication of the papers were grouped into intervals of four to facilitate the visualisation of the information; obtaining a series with a total of six intervals between 1992, the year in which our search detected the first work on IE published in the indexes studied, and 2020 (see Figure 2). As can be observed, the number of publications has been increasing over the last twenty-eight years, going from four publications in the 1992 to 1995 interval to 108 in the most recent period (2016-2020), and with a growing trend in almost the entire series.

INSERT FIGURE 2 HERE

Indexation

As we mentioned in the methodology, the review was made using the journals indexed in JCR, ESCI and SJR. Some of the publications appeared indexed in several of them simultaneously. For our study, we have strictly grouped them into these three, avoiding duplication and following this priority criterion: JCR> SJR> ESCI. Thus, those publications indexed in JCR and SJR have been considered as JCR, and those indexed in SJR and ESCI have been computed as

SJR. In addition, the current indexing of the journal has been considered in order to obtain a more extended search over time, since prior to 2004, there was only JCR, and ESCI was even more recently created (2015). Based on these criteria, we found that 52% of the articles are part of the publications currently indexed in SJR, 41% in JCR and 7% in ESCI.

Orientation, methods and indexation

Most of the articles, a total of 226, are empirical, 36 non-empirical, and two are specific literature reviews. Among the empirical articles, the most widely used methodology is qualitative (77%), followed by those that use quantitative methods (18%) and, lastly, those that use both methodologies (4%).

Specific methods of the empirical works

On the other hand, Figure 3 shows the specific methods used by the works in this review. Some empirical papers used more than one method. The case study methodology is the most numerous, used by a total of 103 articles. It is followed by the ethnographic methodology with 47, the descriptive statistical methodology with 33 articles, the conceptual methodologies (21) and the secondary data (20). Apart from those mentioned, which are the most used; there were detected thirty-two other specific methods, such as cluster analysis, factorial analysis, focus group or word analysis.

INSERT FIGURE 3 HERE

Main journals

The journals where most of the papers were published are *International Journal of Entrepreneurship and Small Business* (27), *Journal of Enterprising Communities: People and Places in the Global Economy* (18), *International Journal of Business and Globalisation* (8), *Journal of Developmental Entrepreneurship* (8), *Journal of Small Business & Entrepreneurship*

(8), *Small Enterprise Research* (7), *Journal of Management & Organization* (7), *Entrepreneurship & Regional Development* (6), *Sustainability* (6), *The International Journal of Entrepreneurship and Innovation* (6), *The International Indigenous Policy Journal* (4), *Tourism Management* (4), *African Journal of Business Management* (3), *Asia Pacific Journal of Tourism Research* (3), *Global Business and Economics Review* (3), *Journal of Small Business Management* (3) and *Journal of Sustainable Tourism* (3).

As can be observed, most of these journals are specifically focused on entrepreneurship, but not specifically on IE. Furthermore, it is detected that almost 17% of the total papers analysed were published in two journals, while the ten journals with the largest number of publications account for almost 38% of the total papers. In addition, a very considerable number of journals only present one publication on this subject.

Main authors

Regarding the authors, the main ones are Dana, L. P. (with 28 papers); Anderson, R. B. (18); Foley, D. and Hindle, K. (6); Dana, T. E., Meis Mason, A., Peredo, A. M., and Vázquez-Maguirre, M. (5); Austin, B. J., Kayseas, B., Mika, J., and Pearson, C. A. (4). A second group of 58 authors have two or three participations (among others, April, W. I.; Kawharu, M.; Moroz, P., Croce, F., etc.) and, finally, we found a last group of 351 authors that only have one paper published in this area. The total number of authors involved with the papers analysed is 421. Furthermore, 37.5% of the papers were written only by one author, 29.2% by two authors, 20.5% by three authors and the rest of the papers were developed by four or more authors.

Unit of analysis

Regarding the unit of analysis studied in the articles, the individual stands out with 47%, followed by the community (32%) and those that analyse companies (11%). There are also some articles with a multiple focus (1%) and country focus (3%), and those of a non-empirical nature whose unit of analysis is not relevant in this regard.

Geographical areas

In relation to the geographical areas and countries, it should be noted that indigenous populations, in many cases, are not strictly limited to the political boundaries drawn internationally. On the contrary, they can live in different countries. However, the analysed papers limit their studies to the populations of certain specific countries, since they are usually very specific populations.

INSERT TABLE 2 HERE

In this way, Table 2 shows the distribution of countries and the number of papers that focus on these countries according to the geographical area to which they belong. We have identified a total of 55 countries where the entrepreneurial indigenous population has been studied. On the other hand, the geographical area with the highest number of works is The Pacific and Indian Ocean (42%). Australia (49) and Canada (45) are the countries where the entrepreneurship of the indigenous population has been most studied, followed by New Zealand (33), USA (19) and Mexico (15).

Subjects and Keywords

There is a high variety of subjects, according to the keywords analysis. This indicates the enormous thematic and contextual diversity in which research on IE is currently built. This is probably due to the influence of the sociocultural issues of the communities studied as well as the environment in which the activity takes place. If the words that are intrinsically related to IE

(entrepreneurship, indigenous entrepreneurship, indigenous, indigenous people, aboriginal and entrepreneurs) are not considered, the most used words are economic development, culture, sustainability and social entrepreneurship. This makes clear the double vision of IE, which tries to combine economic objectives with others more related to social and cultural development.

Main research topics studied

To develop this part of the analysis we have only used the articles that use empirical methodology, as we liked to analyse the empirical findings, and we have classified them according to the main research topic discussed. The studies have been classified into nine research topics, shown in Figure 4. As can be seen, the most analysed research topic is “institutions” (47), followed by “indigenous values and culture” (46) and “non-indigenous culture” (34). At a greater distance, there are “environmentally sustainable activities” (27), “entrepreneurial motivation” (21), “social capital” (18), “personality traits” (17), “education” (10) and “family” (7). Therefore, there is a clear orientation of IE towards the maintenance and development of the culture of their communities, as well as the influence that non-indigenous culture has on these activities or the importance of other institutions as a means of support.

INSERT FIGURE 4 HERE

Next, we summarise the main findings/contributions related to the research topics in which we have grouped the analysed papers.

Institutions

It has been detected that there is a need for greater institutional support that increases the probability of success of IE projects (Alabi, Famakinwa, and Ogunjimi 2017; Singh and Singh 2008; Galbraith and Stiles 2003). It is obvious that this support exists, as evidenced by a number of studies (Anderson et al. 2005; Morrison, Murray, and Ngidang 2006; Papanek 2006; Pascal and

Stewart 2008; Pinto and Blue 2016; Poyser, Scott, and Gilbert 2020; Ramachandran and Shah 1999; Reihana, Sisley, and Modlik 2007; Sabiu et al. 2018; Sullivan and Margaritis 2000; Thakur and Ray 2020; Udén 2008; Zapalska, Perry, and Dabb 2003). However, it does not seem to be enough to implement policies to promote IE; it is necessary that these policies include the indigenous population in their design and management (Bidwell and Murray 2019; Cornell and Kalt 1998; Duile 2020; Hukkinen et al. 2006; Lemelin, Koster, and Youroukos 2015; Mowbray 2006; Nor et al 2017; Reinert 2006; Rout et al. 2017; Vakkayil 2020), respect indigenous culture and values (Anderson 1997; Dana and Remes 2005; Higgins-Desbiolles, Trevorrow, and Sparrow 2014; Tamtik 2020) and preserve the resources and traditional rights of these peoples (Anderson, Dana, and Dana 2006; Chan et al. 2016; Orihuela 2017). In addition, there are also numerous studies that suggest the importance of an interventionist role of the institutions that use entrepreneurship as a mean of social improvement and fight against inequalities (Addinsall et al. 2016; Buckingham and Dana 2005; Cutcher, Ormiston, and Gardner 2020; Gorbuntsova, Dobson, and Palmer 2018; Witbooi and Ukpere 2011), as well as consider entrepreneurship an empowerment instrument (Fröcklin, Jiddawi, and de la Torre-Castro 2018; Gomez 2012; Moyle and Dollard 2008; Pearson and Helms 2010; Vázquez-Maguirre, Camacho Ruelas, and García de la Torre 2016; Vinje 1996).

Indigenous culture and values

First, the largest group of works identified has focused on structuring its analysis around *indigenous culture and values* with different contributions. Indigenous culture is present as a determining factor in all approaches to IE. Specifically, the majority of studies point to indigenous culture and values as the main determinant of IE (among others, Collins et al. 2017; Poirine, Dropsy, and Gay 2017). In addition, they adopt multiple perspectives, such as determination of roles and activities (Dana and Dana 2008), motivation (Wennecke, Jacobsen, and Ren 2019),

objectives (April and Itenge 2020), sociocultural context (Kawharu, Tapsell, and Woods 2017) and marginalisation as an unrecognised people within a State (Chamlee-Wright 2002). In addition, indigenous culture is pointed out as a determinant of the type of entrepreneurship developed from the organisational point of view (Daher, Jaramillo, and Rosati 2020). Several papers that show the influence of collective values on individual ones (April 2008; Hindle and Lansdowne 2005; Pearson and Daff 2013; Spencer et al. 2017). This makes the forms of social and cooperative entrepreneurship the most appropriate to the indigenous culture (Dana 2010; O'Neill 1994; Vázquez-Maguirre 2020a), and also a guarantee of the cultural preservation (Giovannini 2016), including religion (Dana and Anderson 2007). Additionally, it is also pointed out that entrepreneurship acts as an activity that empowers indigenous peoples, and this helps to preserve their culture (Henry 2017; McInnis-Bowers, Parris, and Galperin 2017; Vázquez-Maguirre 2020b).

However, the literature has also identified factors directly related to indigenous values and culture that make entrepreneurship difficult. The first one has to do with the difficulty of managing culture as an intangible resource (Kawharu 2016) and as a source of knowledge (Singh, Singh, and Tag 2008), mainly in relation to the transmission of that knowledge (Capel 2014; Igwe, Madichie, and Amoncar 2020; Widjojo and Gunawan 2020) to future generations (Logue et al. 2018; Masuda 2013). However, we also found a series of authors who point out that the respect for indigenous culture seems fundamental if one wants to undertake a business in the territories dominated by it (Gorman and Vemuri 2017; Johnstone 2008; Ratten and Dana 2015). This acts on many occasions as a limiter of entrepreneurship (Nkongolo-Bakendo et al. 2010), as a barrier to foreign investment (Pinto and Blue 2017), or creates incompatibility with non-indigenous commercial techniques (Curry 2005; Dana 2008). Thus, this shows, in certain cases, the need to break with indigenous culture (Gombay 2006).

Non-indigenous culture

The group made up of works that address *non-indigenous culture* as a main research topic shows in a general way the consequences of the clash between indigenous values and culture (minority) and the conditions of a much broader business context dominated by a non-indigenous culture (majority), indigenous entrepreneurs have to consider two cultures at the same time (Foley 2008a; Foley and O'Connor 2013). Other authors show the difference in objectives and perception of success between indigenous and non-indigenous entrepreneurs (Beaudoin and LeBel 2011; Borges de Lima and Weiler 2015; Mrabure 2019), while it seems clear that the annulment of indigenous culture as a means of promoting entrepreneurship is negative (Atalay 2015). It is, therefore, necessary to promote a coexistence where non-exclusive entrepreneurship models are fostered, stimulating the inclusion of indigenous entrepreneurs from a social and cultural point of view (Amoamo, Ruckstuhl, and Ruwhiu 2018; Anderson 2002; Cornell and Kalt 2000; Denny-Smith and Loosemore 2017; Espeso-Molinero, Carlisle, and Pastor-Alfonso 2016; Foley 2003). This would favour social integration (Gordon, Kayseas, and Moroz 2017) and confront the narrative reality of marginalisation imposed from non-indigenous cultural contexts that are adopted by many indigenous peoples (Ampumuza, Duineveld, and Van der Duim 2020), making indigenous entrepreneurs perceive themselves in numerous occasions as inferior to non-indigenous people (Paulin 2005). Even so, it seems clear that marginalisation is not only the result of a story, but that it exists and is more noticeable in the urban environment, conditioning the activities that they can carry out (Perez and Escalona 2016) and limiting IE, on many occasions, to the informal economy (Meis Mason, Dana, and Anderson 2009).

Another of the lines found in the *non-indigenous culture* group shows the necessary adaptation of indigenous entrepreneurs to non-indigenous culture that set the markets where they must compete if they want to advance beyond a subsistence enterprise (Chen, Parker, and Lin 2006; Briggs 2009; McElwee and Wood 2018; Pérez Velasco Pavón 2014). A balance is required

between commitments to the non-indigenous market and traditional values (Zapalska, Dabb, and Perry 2003), fostering the respect of the non-indigenous context for indigenous values and culture if it is desired that entrepreneurship be promoted (Fowler 2005). This must be done without forgetting that the assimilation of the conventional entrepreneurial spirit does not have to limit cultural identity (Henry, Dana, and Murphy 2018; Venter 2012), and while offering the option of social enterprise as an integrated vehicle of indigenous culture (Sengupta, Vieta, and McMurtry 2015). Finally, in this *non-indigenous culture* group, some studies focus on the gender perspective, showing how indigenous women can suffer marginalisation as entrepreneurs by non-indigenous institutions and culture (Zapalska and Brozik 2017) or by their own indigenous culture as a limitation to their roles or rights (Manzoor 2015). Conversely, specific contexts are also identified where training has fostered the empowerment of indigenous women entrepreneurs and provides them with the tools to use this non-indigenous business training in their indigenous entrepreneurial activity, which is generally a continuation of the activity of their families (Scarborough 2010).

Environmentally sustainable activities

The articles that address *environmentally sustainable activities* as the main research topic show the close relationship with indigenous values and culture to the extent that these peoples identify themselves with the natural resources that they have and the land, which they do not see as a resource but as a whole of which they are part. In fact, environment, economic, and social development are closely intertwined and cannot be separated (Meis Mason, Dana, and Anderson 2012). This means that the preservation of nature is part of its cultural identity (Berkes and Adhikari 2006; Hiedanpää et al. 2020), at the same time that sustainability depends on the survival of the indigenous culture (Swanson and DeVereaux 2017; Vázquez-Maguirre, Portales, and Velásquez Bellido 2018).

Indigenous people are concerned about how to develop viable activities that lead to productive entrepreneurship whilst preserving natural capital (Dana and Mallet 2014). In addition, the literature has identified that IE depends on the natural resources available to indigenous peoples (Meis Mason, Dana, and Anderson 2008, 2009), with traditional activities related to the environment being the main promoters of entrepreneurship among indigenous people (Zander, Austin, and Garnett 2014), along with customary lands and ventures that respect the community and indigenous values (Scheyvens et al. 2017). Moreover, the literature in this area shows that despite the existence of “non-indigenous” activities such as tourism that can favour the preservation of sustainable traditional activities (Leu, Eriksson, and Müller 2018), excessive entrepreneurship related to the environment can limit resources in the long term (Meis Mason, Dana, and Anderson 2007) and result in the environmental destruction driven by non-indigenous industrial activities (Loginov, Ignatyeva, and Naumov 2020; Chang, Su, and Chang 2011). This would result in the economic development and well-being of these populations, since entrepreneurship in environmentally sustainable activities has been shown to be positive (Austin and Garnett 2011; Coral Guerrero 2018; Turner, Berkes, and Turner 2012).

Personality traits

In relation to *personality traits*, studies point out that the individual characteristics of indigenous entrepreneurs can be decisive in the projects undertaken but are always conditioned by the role that the entrepreneur has within the community (Beaudoin, LeBel, and Bouthillier 2009; Simpong et al. 2019) and, in general, by indigenous culture (Austin and Corey 2012; Duffy and Stubben 1998). Hence, it is pointed out in some studies that indigenous entrepreneurs are more likely to undertake cooperatively (Shahidullah and Islam 2018) or to seek innovation under a collective motivation (Pailis, Fatkhurahman, and Arif 2020). On the other hand, studies also show that, apart from the above, in general there are no significant differences in the traits of indigenous

and non-indigenous entrepreneurs (Lee-Ross and Mitchell 2007; Lituchy et al. 2006; Shoebridge, Bultjens, and Peterson 2012). This seems to be the case even for groups such as indigenous women (Dzisi 2008) who have traditional roles that lead them to bear the bulk of family burdens (Diochon 2014). In addition, in any case, studies show the need for a greater professionalization of indigenous entrepreneurs in everything related to business management (Carlisle et al. 2013; Fuller and Cummings 2003).

Social capital

In relation to the works whose main research topic is *social capital*, we find several trends to highlight. In the first place, it seems clear that the creation of networks of entrepreneurs benefits indigenous entrepreneurial projects (Beetson et al. 2020; Rombe 2020; Sridharan et al. 2014; Todd 2012), in line with what was contributed by Foley (2008a) in relation to social capital stock. In addition, this benefit is not limited to entrepreneurship but positively impacts on the progress and improvement of the community's living conditions (Milgram 2020; Vázquez-Maguirre and Portales 2018), favouring prosperity (Henry, Newth, and Spiller 2017; Spencer et al. 2016) and the fight against poverty (Pearson and Helms 2013; Peredo 2003), although there are studies that point out that for this to happen it is necessary to strengthen the community's position in economic development plans (Swinney 2008). In fact, they rely heavily on informal networks, linkages, and trust relationships for their development (Torri 2011). Moreover, studies suggest that community support is necessary for the ongoing entrepreneurial projects (Akbar and Hallak 2019; Barba-Sánchez and Molina 2015), which can be achieved through the creation of social networks that promote the perception of benefit provided to the community (Todd 2012). Although, on some occasions, social capital promotes entrepreneurship only when supportive cultural capital is in place (Light and Dana 2013). However, this is not always possible or without difficulties, since, as evidenced by Camp II, Anderson, and Giberson (2005) there are times when the indigenous

community makes it difficult to create networks beyond the community itself, which is linked to the fact that in many cases the community only encourages entrepreneurship in traditional activities, such as hunting or agriculture, making support from external agents difficult (Dana, Dana, and Anderson 2005), since the break with the traditional culture that is necessary to find such supports usually acts as a barrier (Dlaske 2014) and brought with it the reorganisation of existing societal systems (Movono and Becken 2018).

Entrepreneurial motivation

Regarding motivation, the context will be the determinant of entrepreneurial motivation (Tipu and Sarker 2020), with indigenous culture becoming the main determining factor for the identification of opportunities (Murphy et al. 2020). This identification will be based on unmet needs (Anderson et al. 2004) and cultural perception fixes what is understood by need (Dana 1995), since the identification or response to the opportunity is linked to culture (Dana 1996). Some studies, such as Chang, Tsai, and Chen (2010), suggest that indigenous entrepreneurial motivation does not pursue the search for economic benefits but rather the preservation of a way of life. This sometimes leads to strong contradictions with imposed entrepreneurship models that do not suppose, due to these contradictions, adequate development policies (Smith 2006) or that become a trap due to the lack of the necessary knowledge (Adewusi and Akanle 2020) and that require, in any case, a certain need to adapt the indigenous culture to market opportunities (Muhammad et al. 2020). On the other hand, we have identified a group of studies that specifically point towards an entrepreneurial motivation out of necessity (Ciruela-Lorenzo, González-Sánchez, and Plaza-Angulo 2020; Pilyasov 2020) or that contribute to the identification of specific entrepreneurial opportunities in certain indigenous contexts (Fuller, Buultjens, and Cummings 2005; Hindle et al.

2005; Scheyvens et al. 2020). In most cases, these are ventures based on traditional indigenous resources normally linked to their territory (Weavers et al. 2015).

Education

Studies whose main research topic is *education* show that education favours entrepreneurship by empowering indigenous people and providing them with new perspectives and options for diversifying their traditional activities (Ndemo 2005; Wilson, Gámez Vázquez, and Ivanova 2012). However, for learning programs to be profitable, it is necessary that they adapt to indigenous values and culture and, especially, to their traditional methods of transmitting knowledge (Gainsford and Evans 2020; Liu, Daff, and Pearson 2020), sometimes from parents to son and daughter or between the members of the community (Dana and Light 2011). Moreover, it is necessary that those indigenous values and culture be integrated management practices with general business curricula (Stewart and Pepper 2011). On the other hand, some authors show a need already pointed out by the works that dealt with personality traits: more training in entrepreneurship and business management is needed (Berge 2020; Masuda 2014; Orser and Riding 2016; Willmott 2014) and to ensure that this training and counselling are supervised (Situmorang, Trilaksono, and Japutra 2019).

Family

The works that have addressed *family* as a main research topic show it as the main conditioning factor of IE (Ruiz-Mallén, Fernández-Llamazares, and Reyes-García 2017). A consequence of family participation in community-based activities is that children learn the occupation from a young age (Dana and Light 2011). In fact, in many cases, the indigenous entrepreneur develops the continuation of the activity of their parents (Cruz 2015), and in the case of women this is constituted as an area of informal entrepreneurship (Fowler 2015) and as a response to the needs of the family itself (Aspaas 2004). In addition, there seems to be a certain

tendency to point to the extended family as the place where entrepreneurship arises and where entrepreneurs find the necessary support to start their activity (Morrison 2008), for example, serving them as their own clients (April and Itenge 2020).

Indigenous Entrepreneurship research framework

After the analysis of the main themes studied by the authors, and in order to map the IE phenomena, in Figure 5 we show the IE research framework. From this review emerges two levels. From the macro-level, IE has been studied from four dimensions or perspectives: socio-cultural, economic, intercultural, and institutional. At the micro-level, there have been studied as main drivers of IE: the indigenous culture and values, the personality traits, the community, the family and the motivation. In addition, the main characteristics of the indigenous entrepreneur's ventures, and the main inhibitors and enablers of the IE have been identified.

INSERT FIGURE 5 HERE

According to the conducted systematic literature review, the theoretical underpinnings of IE are: capital theory (April 2008; Austin and Garnett 2011; Dana and Light 2011; Nikolakis 2010; Swinney 2008; Todd 2012; Torri 2011); cultural theory (Foley and O'Connor 2013; Lee-Ross and Mitchell 2007; Poirine, Dropsy and Gay 2017); modernisation, dependency and regulation theories (Buckingham and Dana 2005; Capel 2014; Peredo et al. 2004); the theory of values (Hindle and Lansdowne 2005); opportunity recognition and effectuation theory (Murphy et al. 2020); and theory of sustainable development (Addinsall et al. 2016; Fuller, Buultjens and Cummings 2005; Vázquez-Maguirre 2020a). This reflects the heterogeneity of the different theoretical approaches of IE.

A prospective agenda for future research

In this section, the future lines of research included in the analysed papers and a proposal of lines of advance are summarised. Of the total analysed papers, only 88 included future lines research. The high thematic variety, together with the diversity of contexts and indigenous communities studied, made it difficult to identify common lines of future research (see Figure 6). After analysing these research lines, it was found that more quantitative studies are necessary, although the importance of the sociocultural context will continue to determine and condition the results and, therefore, limits their generalisability. The different research lines reflect a heterogeneity of topics that can be grouped into six different thematic groups.

First, *to extend to other sectors or communities* includes the use of similar methodologies to other sectors or indigenous and non-indigenous communities, in order to conduct comparative studies. Second, *to expand the fields of research*, refers to studies that provide a greater number of cases studied with both qualitative and, especially, quantitative methodology. Third, *impact of IE*, is devoted to expanding the studies of the evaluation of the impact of indigenous entrepreneurial activity and of the policies of promotion of entrepreneurship both in the indigenous communities and in the non-indigenous population. Fourth, the *attributes and indigenous culture* line, deepens the study of the impact of the attributes and traditional characteristics of indigenous communities and their cultural frameworks in entrepreneurship and business activity. These attributes and indigenous culture are considered a factor that is necessary to preserve and promote as the basis to a sustainable development. Fifth, the *entrepreneurial spirit and business value* line, promotes studies that analyse the causes and motivations that encourage entrepreneurship and the acceptance of market organisational values among potential indigenous entrepreneurs. Sixth, *management of indigenous business projects*, broadens the research into the internal management processes of companies and businesses driven by indigenous people. As a conjoint analysis, we put together the

research topics and the lines of research, taken from the literature review (LR), as well as our proposal of lines of advance (see Figure 6).

INSERT FIGURE 6 HERE

Conclusions

This paper contributes to a better understanding of the research field of IE, by summarising a systematic literature review that takes stock of previous literature and proposing relevant lines of advance. A total of 264 papers published since 1992 have been analysed in depth. This number shows an important increase in the number of papers in the last twenty years, which confirms the current interest in this field of study. Most of the analysed papers are empirical (226) and the main used methodology has been the qualitative method. This can be justified by the fact that this methodology allows the immersion of researchers in the reality under study and the analysis of environmental, social and cultural variables that affect the protagonists (Dana 1995), which are of vital importance in the study of IE. In fact, the case study methodology is the most frequent, as it was used by a total of 86 articles. It is followed by the descriptive statistical and the ethnographic methodologies.

The conclusions of this paper are summarised in the following characteristics of the field of IE: heterogeneity and fragmentation, specificity of sociocultural issues and context, concentration in some geographical areas, relevance of the individual level of study, and combination of economic and social objectives. First, regarding *heterogeneity and fragmentation*, despite its great development in the last decades, IE is still an over-fragmented area of research, as can be seen by the heterogeneity of the subjects and the methodologies in the different published

papers. In addition, they have been published in a relatively high number of different journals, most of them with only one publication on the issue. This suggests the need for comparative studies that could increase the generalisability of the conclusions.

Second, regarding *specificity of sociocultural issues and context*, there is an enormous thematic and contextual diversity in which research on IE is currently built. This is due to the influence of the sociocultural issues of the communities studied as well as the context in which the activity takes place. Indigenous entrepreneurs can be considered as cultural ambassadors; they are links between their communities and the world, they preserve community values and revitalise their culture with their business activity. They treasure a traditional knowledge transfer system, where wisdom and skills related to the traditional sources pass from generation to generation. This advocates considering these characteristics as specific to this kind of entrepreneurship.

Third, concerning *concentration in some geographical areas*, Australia, New Zealand and Canada are the contexts most analysed in general terms. There is a group of authors, such as Dana, L. P. and Anderson, R. B., who have published a greater number of studies focused on these countries. Further, in relation to the geographical areas and countries, it should be noted that indigenous populations, in many cases, are not strictly limited to the political boundaries drawn internationally, but the studies analysed do limit their studies to populations of certain specific countries. This suggests the need to carry out larger and more ambitious studies in the future that encompass the reality of entrepreneurship in indigenous populations. This implies analysing the realities of different countries, different political, legal and economic contexts, but the same indigenous community in cultural and identity terms. Consequently, there is a need of empirical cross-country and global studies of IE.

Fourth, regarding *relevance of the individual level of study*, there is a concern for studying IE from an individual point of view, but also from its community or group perspective, since the indigenous culture in general highlights the importance of mutual help and of a work community. Therefore, there is a clear orientation of IE towards the maintenance and development of the culture of their communities, considering also the influence that general culture has on these activities and the importance of other institutions as a means of support. The indigenous entrepreneur has a high level of individual and collective resilience, but indigenous entrepreneurs also have a lack of education and financial resources. Especially nowadays, these communities are extremely vulnerable, and their situation is more difficult with the COVID-19 pandemic. Therefore, in this lies the relevance of the institutional support for the development of incubators/accelerators development initiatives, for example, or in terms of building individual entrepreneurial capacity through formal training and education or helping with the development of social capital (informational and financial networks). This support is crucial to increasing the entrepreneur's capacity of business opportunity identification from their cultural, social and natural heritage, although always respecting the indigenous cultural identity and the sustainable use of its traditional resources.

Fifth, about a *combination of economic and social objectives*, the analysis has shown the combination of economic development, culture and social entrepreneurship. Similar to what Hindle and Moroz (2010) found, this makes clear the double vision of IE, which tries to combine economic objectives with social and cultural development. Through entrepreneurial activity, indigenous people preserve and promote their identity and revitalise their culture. In the same way, entrepreneurship in this context is a self-employment opportunity, and the main business activities are related to natural resources (forestry, poultry or herders, agribusiness and active tourism, among others), so they are environmentally sustainable. This suggests that IE improves economic

development in their communities; and by reducing poverty in indigenous communities, it helps to solve social disparities and improves social well-being. Therefore, their objectives are connected with the Sustainable Development Goals, especially decent work and economic growth, no poverty, and reduced inequalities, among others.

Limitations

As limitations of this paper, firstly, since the research process finished in December 2020, some relevant papers published recently may exist and have not been included in the analysis. However, the most representative studies referring to IE are included, since the main research databases were searched extensively up to this date and the most relevant journals on the topic were browsed. In addition, the mentioned snowballing method allowed us to include other relevant references. Secondly, given the large number of published papers, we based our analysis on a bigger picture of the main research streams and future research lines, so a more detailed analysis of each of the papers, using for example content analysis techniques and concentrating on specific issues, would benefit the integration analysis. In addition, as Croce (2017) pointed out, different IE exists, such as urban, rural and remote. It could be time to conduct specific deeper literature reviews in each of these types. Nonetheless, the conducted analysis provide useful insights about how future studies can advance the field of IE.

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Search Engine	Search criteria
Web of Science (JCR)	Main collection
	Articles
	Search in "theme"
	Search: entrepreneur* AND indigenous OR aborigin*
Web of Science (ESCI)	Main collection
	Articles
	Search in "theme"
	Search: entrepreneur * AND indigenous OR aborigin*
Scopus (SJR)	Journal articles
	Search in "article title, abstract, keywords"
	Search: entrepreneur * AND indigenous OR aborigin*

Table 1. Search criteria

Asia 11,4%	India	10	Central and South America and the Caribbean 13,3%	Peru	11
	Malaysia	6		Bolivia	6
	Japan	4		Guatemala	4
	Pakistan	3		Chile	3
	China	1		Brazil	2
	Laos	1		Colombia	2
	Thailand	1		Costa Rica	2
	Taiwan	1		Ecuador	2
	Tibet	1		Argentina	1
	Turkey	1		Guyana	1
	U. A. E.	1		Honduras	1
The Pacific and Indian Ocean 42%	Australia	49	North America 29,9%	Canada	45
	New Zealand	33		U.S.A.	19
	Indonesia	8		Mexico	15
	Fiji	5	Africa 10,2%	South Africa	6
	Papua New Guinea	4		Nigeria	5
	Hawaii	3		Namibia	3
	Samoa	3		Tanzania	3
	Philippines	2		Uganda	2
	Borneo	1		Cameroon	1
	French Polynesia	1		Gambia	1
	Tahiti	1		Ghana	1
	Vanuatu	1		Guinea	1
	The Artic 4,9%	Finland		4	Kenya
Russia		3	Morocco	1	
Denmark		2	Zambia	1	
Norway		2	Zimbabwe	1	
Sweden		2			

Table 2. Countries studied and number of papers by geographic area

Figure 1. Phases of the methodology

Figure 2. Number of publications per year

Figure 3. Main specific methods used in empirical papers

Figure 4. Main research topics

Figure 5: IE research framework

Figure 6. Summary of relationships